

PREDICTION OF THE COMPRESSION-AFTER-IMPACT STRENGTH OF 2-D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

Paul J. Falzon¹, Israel Herszberg²

¹ *Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd. (CRC-ACS),
506 Lorimer St., Fishermens Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia.*

² *Sir Lawrence Wackett Centre for Aerospace Design Technology, Royal Melbourne Institute
of Technology, GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, Victoria, 3001, Australia.*

SUMMARY: This paper presents an analysis used to predict the compression-after-impact (CAI) strength of 2-D braided carbon/epoxy composites. A closed-form solution, developed to approximate the stress distribution of an orthotropic composite laminate with an elliptical hole loaded in compression, was applied to estimate the stress distribution in the impact damaged braided composite under compression loading. Then, using the semi-empirical point stress failure model, the CAI strength was predicted. Comparisons made between predicted and measured CAI strengths revealed good agreement, with differences less than 10% in most cases. The use of such models to predict failure of composites made from unidirectional prepreg is of little advantage because the characteristic length depends on the ply orientation, hole size and hole aspect ratio. A major finding from this work is that for braided composites, one characteristic length (determined from experiment) was applicable for a range of damage geometries and braid architectures.

KEYWORDS: braided composites, CAI strength, characteristic length, impact

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composite materials have been successfully employed as structural materials for various applications. These composites have shown superior performance over metals in applications requiring high strength/stiffness, excellent fatigue and corrosion resistance, as well as low weight. However, a major concern with composite materials is their susceptibility to impact damage. Unlike metallic materials, composites can suffer a significant reduction in mechanical performance due to impact damage. Methods which have been used to address this problem include the application of toughened resins and the introduction of through-thickness fibre reinforcement. Well established and highly automated processes developed for the textile industry, such as braiding [1], have the capability to fabricate near net-shape preforms of the desired fibre orientations and necessary through-thickness reinforcement. Combined with a liquid moulding technique, there is the potential to produce reliable low-cost, high-quality components with improved damage tolerance.

To investigate the damage resistance and tolerance of braided composites, a series of low-velocity drop-weight impact tests were performed on 2-D braided carbon/epoxy laminates [2]. Damaged specimens were then loaded in compression to measure their compression-after-impact (CAI) strength [2]. This paper presents an analysis used to predict the CAI strength of 2-D braided carbon/epoxy composites measured from these tests.

Impact damage introduced into a composite laminate results in a significant reduction in stiffness in the damaged area, causing load to be redistributed to the undamaged region. This redistribution of load results in a stress concentration, similar to that expected of a panel with an open hole. In fact, the CAI damage behaviour found in the braided specimens was similar to that observed in composite panels with holes loaded in compression. A closed-form solution, developed to approximate the stress distribution of an orthotropic composite laminate with an elliptical hole loaded in compression, was applied to estimate the stress distribution in the impact damaged braided composite under compression loading. Then, using the semi-empirical point stress and average stress failure models, the CAI strength was predicted.

MATERIALS

A series of four different braid architectures have been considered in this study. Compression specimens were prepared from panels manufactured from 2-D triaxially braided preforms. The specimens tested are summarised in Table 1. The braided preforms were manufactured from 12K AS4 carbon fibre tows using a 72 carrier Wardwell braider at the Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware. They were manufactured as a tubular preform then cut open to form a flat preform. The specimens were consolidated using Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) with Ciba Geigy RTM6 epoxy resin system. Note that specimen types BR-45a and BR-45b have identical fibre orientations, although BR-45b was a tighter braid.

Table 1: Summary of composite materials used in this study

Laminate I.D.	Nominal Thick. (mm)	Fibre Volume Fraction (%)	Laminate Construction	No. of plies	Percentage of 0° fibres
BR-45a	2.1	58	0°/±45° braid	5	26.1
BR-45b	2.1	58	0°/±45° braid	4	26.1
BR-60	2.1	58	0°/±60° braid	4	20.0
BR-LA	2.1	58	0°/±45° braid	3	41.4

EXPERIMENT

A series of low-velocity drop-weight impact tests were performed on 2-D braided carbon/epoxy composites followed by compression tests on the damaged specimens. A brief description of the tests methods and findings is given in this section. Detailed results have been published elsewhere by Falzon et al. [2].

Impact Test

Impact testing of low to medium impact energy levels (up to 7 J/mm), were carried out on specimens measuring 92 x 117 mm using an instrumented drop weight test rig [2]. The specimens were clamped using a support frame with a test window measuring 80 x 90 mm. The impactor, which had a hemispherical steel tup 12.5 mm in diameter and variable weights ranging between 200 and 1200 grams, was dropped from heights of up to 2 m to impact the specimens at various energy levels. Only one impact was performed at each energy level.

Impacted specimens were then ultrasonically C-scanned to quantify the extent of damage introduced into the specimens due to the impact event.

Ultrasonic C-scans revealed that post-impact damage zones of all specimens exhibited a quasi-circular, almost elliptical, shape for all energy levels considered (Fig. 1). Visual inspection of the impacted specimens revealed that the sustained damage was due primarily to the delamination of plies. On the impacted surface of the braided specimens, at energy levels exceeding 3 J/mm, there was evidence of compressive cracking which took the form of an indentation. The opposite face of the specimens exhibited fibre break-out or tensile splitting. Crack propagation tended to follow fibre directions and stop at fibre tow cross-over points.

Fig. 1: Typical C-scans of an impacted 2-D braided composite (Impact energy ≈ 4.5 J/mm)

Compression-After-Impact Test

The test rig used to measure the compression strengths of the impacted specimens [2] comprises three separate components - lower and upper clamping blocks between which the specimen is set for testing, a pair of anti-buckling face plates with a 40 mm diameter central window to ensure the impact damage zone is not restricted from propagating during the test, and a die press with a ball-and-cup arrangement to ensure the specimen is loaded axially. The specimens were loaded at a rate of 0.5 mm/min and the tests were terminated at the first onset of failure. Failure was defined as the first sudden drop in load.

In all the specimens tested, failure initiated at the impacted region and progressed in a direction transverse to the loading direction, with little or no damage growth in the load direction. The indentation of the impact site and the area of fibre breakage reduced the stiffness across the damage area causing load to be redistributed into the undamaged region, thus increasing the stresses around the damage site. Global failure of the damaged specimens occurred as a result of the kink band mechanism, and not from sub-laminate buckling as is found in unidirectional prepreg materials. This redistribution of load at the impact site results in a stress concentration, similar to that expected of a panel with an open hole. In fact, the CAI damage behaviour found in the braided specimens was similar to that observed in composite panels with holes loaded in compression. Soutis and Curtis [3] also found the CAI damage pattern in laminated composites to be similar to that observed in laminated plates

with open holes loaded in compression. The variation of CAI strength with damage width for all the specimens tested can be seen in Figures 4 to 7. Damage width is defined in Fig. 1.

MODELLING APPROACH

Impact damage introduced into a composite laminate results in a significant reduction in stiffness in the damaged area, resulting in a complex stress distribution surrounding the damaged zone. The reduction in compression strength is a result of this stress concentration. Attempts at predicting the reduced strength or CAI strength encompasses models of varying degrees of sophistication. Statistical methods have been proposed by Guild et al. [4] and Prichard and Hogg [5] which relate CAI strength with damage width using linear regression. Soutis and Curtis [3] applied their cohesive zone model, developed initially to predict notched compressive strengths, to estimate the CAI strength of some prepreg composites. Others [6] have modelled the damaged area as a soft inclusion. One approach proposed by Xiong and Poon [7] involved modelling the damaged area as a soft elliptical inclusion. Then using a complex variable method outlined by Lekhnitskii [8], the in-plane stresses can be calculated. The CAI strength of the laminates is then predicted using an empirical failure criterion.

To predict the CAI strength of the braided composites, a similar approach was adopted. The difference being rather than modelling the damage as a soft inclusion, it was conservatively assumed that the damage area behaved as an elliptical opening or hole. That is, the material in the damaged area does not provide any load carrying capacity. As mentioned earlier, the CAI damage behaviour found in the braided specimens was similar to that observed in composite panels with holes loaded in compression. The accuracy of this assumption is dependent on the extent of impact damage. The assumption is more accurate in cases where impact damage causes fibre fracture or penetration compared with events where impact loading causes internal delaminations with only barely visible impact damage. The idealisation of an impacted braided composite panel is illustrated in Fig. 2. The dimensions of the elliptical holes ($2a$ and $2b$) used in the analysis are measured from ultrasonic C-scan results, like that shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2: Idealised impact damage in a composite panel represented as an elliptical hole

The exact solution of the stress distribution of an infinite orthotropic composite laminate with an elliptical hole has been presented by Lekhnitskii [8]. This solution was approximated by Tan [9] to express the stress distribution in a simple closed-form solution. Using this closed-form solution with appropriate failure criteria, the CAI strength can be predicted. Two criteria used in this work include the point stress and average stress failure models, developed by Whitney and Nuismer [10,11].

Point Stress Failure Model

The point stress failure model assumes that failure would occur when the stress at a characteristic length, b_0 , ahead of the damage first reaches the undamaged compressive strength of the laminate, σ_0 . Using this criterion along with the approximate stress distribution of an infinite orthotropic symmetric laminate containing an elliptical opening [11], then the CAI strength, σ_{CAI} , may be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{CAI} = \sigma_0 \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2} (\xi_1^{-1} + \sqrt{\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2})} + \frac{\lambda^2 (1 + \lambda) (\xi_1^{-1} + 2\sqrt{\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2})}{(\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2)^{3/2} (\xi_1^{-1} + \sqrt{\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2})^2} - \frac{\lambda^7}{2} \left(K_T - 1 - \frac{2}{\lambda} \right) \times \left[\frac{5\xi_1^{-1}}{(\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{7\lambda^2 \xi_1^{-1}}{(\xi_1^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2)^{9/2}} \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\lambda = b/a \quad (2)$$

$$\xi_1 = a/(a + b_0) \quad (3)$$

$$K_T = K_T^\infty \left/ \left[\frac{\lambda^2}{(1-\lambda)^2} + \frac{(1-2\lambda)}{(1-\lambda)^2} \sqrt{1 + (\lambda^2 - 1)(2a/W)^2} - \frac{\lambda^2}{(1-\lambda)} \frac{(2a/W)^2}{\sqrt{1 + (\lambda^2 - 1)(2a/W)^2}} \right] \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\lambda^7}{2} \left(\frac{2a}{W} \right)^6 \left(K_T^\infty - 1 - \frac{2}{\lambda} \right) \left\{ \left[1 + (\lambda^2 - 1) \left(\frac{2a}{W} \right)^2 \right]^{-5/2} - \left(\frac{2a}{W} \right)^2 \left[1 + (\lambda^2 - 1) \left(\frac{2a}{W} \right)^2 \right]^{-7/2} \right\} \right. \quad (4)$$

Where λ denotes the hole aspect ratio of the major and minor diameters, $2a$ and $2b$ respectively; b_0 is a characteristic length to be determined empirically; W is the width of the panel; K_T is the stress concentration factor for a finite width panel; and K_T^∞ is the stress concentration factor for an infinitely wide panel, which is expressed as follows [11]:

$$K_T^\infty = 1 + \frac{1}{\lambda} \sqrt{2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_y}{E_x}} - \nu_{xy} \right) + \frac{E_y}{G_{xy}}} \quad (5)$$

where E_x and E_y are the laminate in-plane stiffnesses in the respective x and y (loading) directions respectively, ν_{xy} is the in-plane Poisson's ratio and G_{xy} is the in-plane shear modulus.

Average Stress Failure Model

The average stress failure model assumes that failure would occur when the averaged laminate stress over a characteristic length, a_0 , away from the edge of the damage first reaches the undamaged compressive strength of the laminate. Using this criterion along with the approximate stress distribution of an infinite orthotropic symmetric laminate containing an elliptical opening [11], then σ_{CAI} may be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{CAI} = \sigma_0 \left\{ \frac{\lambda^2}{(1-\lambda)^2} \xi_2^{-1} + \frac{(1-2\lambda)}{(1-\lambda)^2} \sqrt{\xi_2^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2} - \frac{\lambda^2}{(1-\lambda)\sqrt{\xi_2^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2}} + \frac{\lambda^7}{2} \left(K_T - 1 - \frac{2}{\lambda} \right) \times \left[\frac{1}{(\xi_2^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2)^{5/2}} - \frac{\lambda^2}{(\xi_2^{-2} - 1 + \lambda^2)^{7/2}} \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

where,

$$\xi_2 = a/(a + a_0) \quad (7)$$

λ and K_T have been defined in Eqns 2 and 4, respectively, and a_0 is a characteristic length to be determined empirically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theoretical predictions of the CAI strength were made using damage dimensions obtained from C-scans along with the elastic properties for each of the braid architectures tested. The critical parameter in the calculations is the characteristic length, which was determined empirically for the two stress models. Fig. 3 shows the variation of characteristic length with damage width. The characteristic lengths were determined so as to obtain an exact correlation between the predicted and measured CAI strength for each data point. It can be seen that there is a linear relationship between the characteristic length and the damage width for the average stress model, whereas the characteristic length is independent of damage width for the point stress model.

The criteria used in selecting the characteristic length included keeping it independent of damage size, damage aspect ratio and braid architecture, while maintaining good correlation between measured and predicted CAI strengths. Although the correlation could be further improved by using different characteristic lengths for different braid architectures, it is the authors opinion that a constant characteristic length value, which may sacrifice some accuracy, is of considerably more use. Establishing a constant characteristic length removes the necessity to perform tests to determine a new characteristic length for a new braid architecture. Using this philosophy, only the point stress model was used to predict the CAI strength of braided composites. Using the values shown in Fig. 3, an average characteristic length of 5.31 mm with a standard deviation of 1.52 mm was calculated.

Comparisons between the measured CAI strengths and those predicted by the point stress model are shown in Figures 4 to 7. Predictions for three characteristic lengths were calculated, based on the average characteristic length ($b_0 = 5.31$ mm) and the upper and lower deviations ($b_0 = 6.83$ mm and $b_0 = 3.79$ mm respectively). As can be seen, the point stress model

adequately predicts the CAI strength using the average characteristic length, where in most cases the differences are less than 10%. There are only a few cases where discrepancies exceed 15%. The upper and lower deviations illustrate that the point stress analysis is not very sensitive to the characteristic length and is a major reason why a constant characteristic length is applicable.

Fig. 3: Variation of characteristic length with damage width for all specimens

Fig. 4: Comparison of predicted and measured CAI strengths for BR-45a specimens

Fig. 5: Comparison of predicted and measured CAI strengths for BR-45b specimens

Fig. 6: Comparison of predicted and measured CAI strengths for BR-60 specimens

Although further testing would be required to substantiate the findings, the fact that a common characteristic length could be used to predict the CAI strength of different braid architectures of a limited number of damage geometries, is a major finding. This is not the case with prepreg composites. Naik [12], in his compression strength modelling of prepreg

composite panels with holes, used different characteristic dimensions for a range of stacking sequences and lay-ups. While Tan et al. [13], who performed tension tests on carbon/epoxy prepreg panels with elliptical holes, shows there is a need to change the characteristic length as the size of the hole increases. Tan et al. [13] empirically formulated relationships between characteristic length, hole size, and hole aspect ratio to improve the correlation between predicted and measured notch strengths. One reason for the need to vary the characteristic length for prepreg composites is the change in failure mechanism which occurs for different lay-ups and hole geometries. Fortunately for the braided specimens studied there was no apparent need to vary the characteristic length. This is due to the non-sensitivity of the analysis as explained earlier, and may physically be due to the fact that there was no change in failure mechanism, or that the range of damage sizes modelled was not large enough to reveal any dependencies on damage geometry.

Fig. 7: Comparison of predicted and measured CAI strengths for BR-LA specimens

CONCLUSIONS

A method was proposed to predict the CAI strength of 2-D braided carbon/epoxy composites. The model involves idealising the impact damage in the braided composite as an elliptical hole. Using the semi-empirical point stress failure criterion, which necessitates the use of a characteristic length, the CAI strength was predicted for a range of architectures investigated in this study. Comparisons made between predicted and measured CAI strengths revealed good agreement, with differences less than 10% in most cases.

A major finding from this work, which would need to be substantiated with further testing, is that for braided composites, one characteristic length (determined from experiment) was applicable for the range of damage geometries and braid architectures investigated in this study. This is not the case with composites made from unidirectional prepreg, where the characteristic length depends on the ply orientation, hole size and hole aspect ratio.

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